

Cation Exchange and Selectivity Behaviour of Trace-elements between Colloidal Clays and Resins as a Function of the Concentration of the Dispersed Phase

A. K. Nag and A. Chatterjee

Exchange studies have been made between varying amounts of H-resin and varying concentrations of clays associated with the trace elements chromium, manganese and iron and also with the mono-valent element lithium. Lithium is selected to see the effect of ion-hydration on the ease of exchange. Selectivity co-efficients have also been calculated from the exchange data at different clay concentrations.

The exchange of ions and selectivity co-efficients are found to decrease with the concentration of the clay suspension. The decrease is attributed to the overlapping of electrical double layer and subsequent immobilization of ions. The rate of decrease of ion exchange and selectivity co-efficients becomes less prominent as the clay concentration increases. This is more marked in case of Cr and Li-Clays. This may be due to the ion hydration and subsequent prevention of electrical double layers.

Some of the isotherms obtained with the varying amounts of H-ions in H-resin are similar in shape to ordinary adsorption isotherms and some of them are somewhat reversed in shape to ordinary adsorption isotherms and similar to those obtained by other ions.

It has been well established that plant roots adsorb ions from the soils by a process of ion exchange. Various attempts have been made to study the exchange property of clays by artificial means. The procedure usually adopted for this purpose simulates little of the conditions obtaining in the plant root zone. For instance, the exchange of ions is usually studied in diluted systems and that, too, in the presence of perhaps foreign electrolytes at a concentration quite inconceivable in the root zone. The usual practice is to extrapolate or apply, as it is, the information gained under the artificial conditions to the natural soil root system. Brown and Albrecht¹ and later on Chatterjee² adopted a new method to study the exchange property of the soils by artificial means. Their method simulates almost soil-root system. It consists in having a H-system (clay or plant root) separated by a suitable membrane (collodion or cellophane) from the soil colloid saturated with one or more kinds of ions. The membrane does not seem to interfere with the exchange. Moreover the soil root condition can easily be simulated.

On the basis of their studies, Brown and Albrecht (*loc. cit.*) and Chatterjee³ showed that ions on the clay surface differ in the ease with which they exchange with the H-ions of the root system. Chatterjee (*loc. cit.*) and later on Nag and Chatterjee⁴ carried out the

1. A. D. Brown and W. A. Albrecht, *Res. Bull.*, No. 477, College of Agric. Univ. of Mo (1950).
2. A. Chatterjee, *Journal Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1954, 2.
3. A. Chatterjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 591.
4. A. K. Nag and A. Chatterjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 101.

exchange experiments between H-resin and clays saturated with common ions as well as trace elements usually found present in soils. In the present investigation, the exchange characteristics of trace elements chromium, manganese and iron present in soils are studied at different concentrations of the base saturated clays and their selectivity co-efficients are also calculated. Lithium clay is also used to see the behaviour of ion hydration on the ease of exchange when measured against the concentration of the clay salt.

The selectivity co-efficients as defined by different workers^{5,6,7} are calculated by dividing the ratio of the concentrations raised to appropriate powers of the two ions involved in the exchange reaction in one phase to that in the other. It is thus simply the equilibrium constant of the reversible exchange reactions, such as

ions.

The equilibrium constants can be represented as usual by,

$$K_A^B = \frac{[B^+]_R [A^+]_M}{[A^+]_R [B^+]_M} = \frac{[B^+]_R / [A^+]_R}{[B^+]_M / [A^+]_M}$$

$$K_D^C = \frac{[C^{2+}]_R [D^+]^2_M}{[D^+]^2_R [C^{2+}]_M} = \frac{[C^{2+}]_R / [D^+]^2_R}{[C^{2+}]_M / [D^+]^2_M}$$

or,

$$K_D^C = \frac{[C^{2+}]^{\frac{1}{2}}_R [D^+]_M}{[D^+]_R [C^{2+}]^{\frac{1}{2}}_M} = \frac{[C^{2+}]^{\frac{1}{2}}_R / [D^+]_R}{[C^{2+}]^{\frac{1}{2}}_M / [D^+]_M} = \sqrt{K_D^C}$$

$$K_X^Y = \frac{[Y^{3+}]_R [X^+]^3_M}{[X^+]^3_R [Y^{3+}]_M} = \frac{[Y^{3+}]_R / [X^+]^3_R}{[Y^{3+}]_M / [X^+]^3_M}$$

or

$$K_X^Y = \frac{[Y^{3+}]^{1/3}_R [X^+]_M}{[X^+]_R [Y^{3+}]^{1/3}_M} = \frac{[Y^{3+}]^{1/3}_R / [X^+]_R}{[Y^{3+}]^{1/3}_M / [X^+]_M} = \sqrt[3]{K_X^Y}$$

where the expressions in parenthesis denote concentration and subscripts R and M denote the two solid exchanger phases viz., synthetic resin exchanger and montmorillonite clay respectively. These quantities are also termed as selectivity co-efficients.

5. C. E. Marshall and Garcia, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 1663.
6. A. N. Basu, B. K. Seal and S. K. Mukherjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 71.
7. A. Chatterjee and S. K. Mukherjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 673.

The selectivity co-efficients obtained either with one ion in the solid exchanger and the other ion in solution or with both the ions being present as exchangeable ions in the solid exchangers, are not expected to be constant, when concentrations are used in place of activity, although some of the workers have claimed it to be so.

In the present investigation, the complicating effects of complex formation is avoided, by selecting two solid exchangers, the resin phase simulating plant root and montmorillonite clay saturated with trace element cations. The selectivity co-efficients will obviously depend on the relative abundance of ions and their relative affinities towards the exchangers.

EXPERIMENTAL

The H-clay was prepared by the usual method of electro dialysis of the clay fraction ($< 2\mu$) isolated from a sample of Gujrat bentonite. The b.e.c. and the pH of 3.17% colloidal suspension as determined before (*loc. cit.*) were found to be 96.0 ± 0.2 and 3.67 respectively. Cr, Mn and Fe clays were prepared by leaching the H-clay at $pH = 3.67$ with 0.5 (M) solution of $Cr_2(SO_4)_3$, $MnSO_4$ and $FeCl_3$ solutions respectively. Usually the leaching was continued for 3-4 days. It was then washed free of the electrolytes by centrifuging it with as small an amount of acidulated water ($pH = 4$) as possible, in instalments till the leached water was free from electrolytes. This was necessary to prevent the hydrolysis of the clay salts. The clay salts were then suspended in double distilled water in pyrex bottles.

Li-clay was prepared by adding calculated amount of extra pure reagent grade $Li_2CO_3^*$ to a known volume of H-clay suspension of known strength and boiling off the CO_2 from the mixture.

Reaction between H-resin and Cr-clay

TABLE I

Amount of resin corresponding to	Total $Cr^{3+} = 42$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 0.96% $pH = 3.56$		Total $Cr^{3+} = 42$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 2.2% $pH = 3.2$		Total $Cr^{3+} = 42$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 3.92% $pH = 3.0$		Total $Cr^{3+} = 42.5$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 5.74% $pH = 4.04$	
	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Cr^{3+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Cr^{3+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Cr^{3+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Cr^{3+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient
1) 0.5S	17.45(3.48)	3.2×10^{-5}	8.8 (2.94)	0.0995	6.6 (2.8)	0.0179	5.5 (3.58)	0.0067
2) 1.0S	16.33(2.86)	0.1637	10.6 (2.80)	0.0129	10.9 (2.76)	0.0151	8.52(3.42)	0.0042
3) 1.5S	16.8 (2.84)	0.0321	13.32(2.63)	0.1000	10.28(2.64)	0.0036	8.16(3.38)	8.12×10^{-4}
4) 2.0S	21.1 (2.76)	3.89×10^{-5}	17.6 (2.62)	0.0134	11.16(2.62)	0.0013	11.14(3.35)	0.0013

* Obtained through the courtesy of Prof. P. C. Mukherjee, Presidency College, Calcutta.

Amberlite 1R-120 resin was converted into the H-form by usual method. The experimental procedure for the study of the exchange between the H-resin and the base saturated clays at various concentrations was the same as described by Chatterjee in earlier papers (*loc. cit.*).

The selectivity co-efficients $K_{H^+}^{M^{2+}}$, $K_{H^+}^{M^+}$ and $K_{H^+}^{M^{3+}}$, where M^{2+} denotes Mn^{2+} , M^+ denotes Li^+ , and M^{3+} denotes Fe^{3+} Cr^{3+} were calculated from exchange data. The figures in the bracket are the equilibrium *pH* values of the clays.

TABLE II

Reaction between H-resin and Mn-clay

Amount of resin corresponding to	Total $Mn^{2+} = 80$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 1.35% <i>pH</i> = 3.9		Total $Mn^{2+} = 82$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 2.63% <i>pH</i> = 3.8		Total $Mn^{2+} = 80$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 4.5% <i>pH</i> = 3.74		Total $Mn^{2+} = 80$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 7.3% <i>pH</i> = 3.68	
	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Mn^{2+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Mn^{2+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Mn^{2+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Mn^{2+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient
1) 0.5S	36.8(2.92)	0.1376	28.6(3.44)	2.8658	27.0(3.08)	2.23	16.7(3.18)	0.0369
2) 1.0S	44.3(2.90)	1.6181	33.5(2.96)	0.3273	27.5(3.04)	0.1441	28.5(2.70)	0.1694
3) 1.5S	47.2(2.86)	0.5256	32.8(2.95)	0.0884	28.6(2.92)	0.0546	30.0(2.70)	0.066
4) 2.0S	56.0(2.74)	0.5853	45.3(2.93)	0.1808	45.0(2.58)	0.1968	31.2(2.68)	0.0552

TABLE III

Reaction between H-resin and Fe^{3+} clay

Amount of resin corresponding to	Total $Fe^{3+} = 44$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 1.56% <i>pH</i> = 3.84		Total $Fe^{3+} = 44$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 2.06% <i>pH</i> = 3.46		Total $Fe^{3+} = 45$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 4.25% <i>pH</i> = 3.11		Total $Fe^{3+} = 44$ meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 7.6% <i>pH</i> = 2.94	
	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Fe^{3+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Fe^{3+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Fe^{3+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions re-placed by Fe^{3+} ions	Selectivity co-efficient
1) 0.5S	17.2 (3.17)	29.63	18.13(3.06)	32.04	7.42(2.9)	6.4×10^{-4}	6.34(2.86)	0.0112
2) 1.0S	26.1 (3.10)	4.35	19.01(2.97)	0.2452	13.2 (2.83)	0.034	12.86(2.82)	0.0289
3) 1.5S	33.6 (3.10)	3.61	19.5 (2.92)	0.0082	15.45(2.80)	0.0154	15.3 (2.79)	0.0264
4) 2.0S	42.0 (3.04)	15.99	20.5 (2.85)	0.0191	17.9 (2.75)	0.0114	16.87(2.72)	0.00829

TABLE IV

Reaction between H-resin and Li-clay

Amount of resin corresponding to	Total Li ⁺ = 94 meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 0.94% pH = 9.7		Total Li ⁺ = 94 meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 1.23% pH = 10.16		Total Li ⁺ = 94 meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 2% pH = 9.2		Total Li ⁺ = 96 meq/ 100 gms. dry clay strength = 3.36% pH = 8.82	
	Meq of H-ions replaced by Li ⁺ ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions replaced by Li ⁺ ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions replaced by Li ⁺ ions	Selectivity co-efficient	Meq of H-ions replaced by Li ⁺ ions	Selectivity co-efficient
1) 0.5S	11.19(9.4)	0.0411	9.65(9.5)	0.0288	6.47(7.78)	0.0115	10.0115(7.83)	0.0349
2) 1.0S	19.18(9.1)	0.0639	15.8 (9.40)	0.0388	11.04(7.26)	0.0172	9.83(7.21)	0.0130
3) 1.5S	21.25(9.0)	0.0504	19.48(9.35)	0.0408	12.16(7.01)	0.0175	10.85(6.91)	0.0103
4) 2.0S	25.5 (8.9)	0.0404	20.32(9.32)	0.0325	12.82(6.6)	0.0112	11.18(6.6)	0.0081

DISCUSSION

The nature of variation of ion-exchange and the selectivity co-efficient of the ions with the concentration of clay and also with the amount of H-resin i.e., the concentration of H⁺-ion in the resin phase are shown in the figs. 1 and 2. The amount of H-resin have been expressed in terms of symmetry concentration in the tables.

The influence of concentration on the ease of replacement of the cations associated with the clay for the H⁺-ion of the H-resin is clearly noticeable from Fig. 1(b).

In case of Cr-clay the rate of exchange diminishes as the clay concentration increases upto the clay concentration studied although at higher concentration the curve is less steep.

In case of Mn-clay, the rate of exchange is much higher than that of other clay salts which may be due to the larger amount of manganese being initially present in the clay salt. In this case, the nature of variation of exchange with the clay concentration is similar to that of Cr-clay, the only difference is that here the rate of fall is very sharp and this is maintained throughout particularly when we consider the systems, using 0.5 and 1.5 symmetry concentration of H-resin used.

In case of Fe-clay, the rate of exchange initially falls very sharply as the clay concentration increases, then remains almost constant, the notable exception being the system using the least amount of H-resin where the rate of exchange initially increases and ultimately it attains a more or less steady value.

The rate of exchange in case of Li-clay is similar to that of Cr-clay. It decreases steadily up to the clay concentration of 2.0% and then remains practically constant up to nearly 3.5% beyond which the clay becomes very viscous and measurements could not be carried out.

The decrease in the rate of exchange with the clay concentration may be attributed to the overlapping of the double layer and consequent "immobilization" of ions. The small decrease in the case of Cr and Li-clay systems may be due to the hydration of ions which are known to form heavily hydrated ions in aqueous solution (*loc. cit.*). The molecules of water of hydration associated with these ions prevent the overlapping of the double layers when the sol is concentrated that results in small decrease in the rate of exchange.

Section (a) of Fig. 1 represents the amount of cation exchanged as a function of the symmetry concentration of H-ions in the H-resin. The slopes of the isotherms in case of Cr-clay and in case of some of the Mn-clay systems are similar to those of bivalent ions

as measured earlier (*loc. cit.*) and the slopes of the other isotherms are similar to those obtained with electrolytes, the notable exceptions being those of 1.56% and 2.06% Fe-clay where the isotherms are almost straight lines.

The selectivity co-efficients when plotted against clay concentration in Fig. 2(b) also follow the same nature. The values for Mn and Fe-clay decreases sharply with the increase of clay concentration up to some extent, then remains practically constant (*loc. cit.*). In case of Fe-clay when exchanged for the minimum amount of H-ions associated with H-resin, the selectivity value slightly increases initially and then follows the same nature. The selectivity co-efficient values of Cr and Li-clays with the H-resin also show a decrease with the increasing clay concentration, but here the rate is very small and in case of Cr-clay, in addition, it shows a slight initial increase. The decrease in selectivity co-efficients with increasing clay concentration may be traced to the same reason as that of overlapping of double layers between two contiguous phases as the clay becomes concentrated. The small decrease in case of Cr and Li-clay may be due to the hydration effect of ions.

The selectivity co-efficient is also plotted as a function of symmetry concentration of the H^+ ions in the hydrogen resin [Sec. (a) in Fig. 2]. An initial decrease followed by an increase is observed in case of Mn-clay, whereas Fe-clay shows a decrease and ultimately a more or less constant value is attained.

The curves obtained with the Li-clay are horizontal in nature showing that the values are almost constant throughout the symmetry concentrations studied.

Sincere thanks of the authors are due to Prof. S. C. Shome, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta for providing laboratory facilities.

Department of Chemistry,
Serampore College, Serampore,
and
Department of Chemistry,
Presidency College, Calcutta.

Received September 28, 1967,